

Structural analysis of healthy and degenerated intervertebral discs using meshless methods

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Abstract

Intervertebral disc (IVD) degeneration is a progressive condition that modifies the geometric morphology, biomechanical behavior, and material properties of an IVD, affecting its ability to transmit and distribute loads. The aim of this work is to analyze the effects of applying different loads in different orientations both in healthy and degenerated IVDs. To perform the numerical analysis, a three-dimensional (3D) discretized model was constructed and analyzed with the radial point interpolation method (RPIM) and the finite element method (FEM). In order to simulate the IVD degeneration, the mechanical properties, height and applying loads were altered, allowing to represent six different study cases. With an elasto-static analysis, assuming small strains, the von Mises equivalent stress and principal stresses (σ_1 and σ_3) variable fields were obtained with both RPIM and FEM. Also, for a region of interest, the equivalent strain is also addressed. The results show that distinct IVD conditions lead to distinct stress/strain distributions. Additionally, the comparison between the RPIM and FEM solutions indicate that the RPIM provides variable fields with lower magnitude. Nevertheless, both technique provide similar variable field distributions.

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1 Introduction

Over 80% of the adult population experiences low back pain (LBP) at some point in their lives, resulting in a vast amount of money in annual costs, to alleviate and treat this pain [1],[2]. Epidemiologic and biomechanical studies have shown that mechanical loads imposed on the human spine and, consequently, on the intervertebral disc (IVD), during daily life, play a significant role in this type of pain [2].

The IVDs are fibrocartilaginous, biconvex lens-shaped structures, which are interposed between the vertebral bodies of two adjacent vertebrae and are responsible for approximately 25% of the size of the spine [3]. The IVD is constituted by a soft, deformable, nucleus pulposus (NP) that is surrounded by the fibrous concentric layers of the anulus fibrosus (AF) [4],[5]. The NP and AF are comprised primarily of water, proteoglycans, and collagen fibers, in different ratios between the two tissues [6]. They function as an additional load-absorption support that sustains high deformations, distributes the load, allows movement of the functional unit, and prevents friction between adjacent bodies [7],[4]. Throughout human life, a phenomenon called disc degeneration occurs, which is marked by changes in the disc morphology and biochemistry [8]. For example, when compared to a healthy disc, a degenerated one can have a 20% to 60% reduction of its height, depending on the degree of degeneration [9]. Upon disc degeneration, there is a reduction in the water content in the NP, which leads to changes in its mechanical properties. For this reason, it is possible to make a comparison between a hydrated disc, when it is healthy, and dehydrated, when it is degenerated [10],[11].

IVD pressure is an important parameter to characterize spinal overload in disc degeneration [12]–[14]. To analyze the effects of this degeneration in the IVD, several studies have already been carried out. In the 1960s and 1970s, the pioneering scientific work performed by Nachemson et al. [15] showed a relationship between body positions or exercises (unsupported sitting, lifting weights, etc.) and lumbar IVD pressure. In this study, Nachemson and colleagues showed that sitting increases the pressure in the IVD by approximately 40% when compared with standing position [15]. A few years ago, finite element method (FEM) analysis emerged as a promising solution to study IVD pressure and its relationship to healthy and degenerated IVDs. Cai et al. [9], proved, using a finite element study, that an increase in the IVD degeneration leads to higher von Mises stress and higher shear stress [9]. This fact was also proved by Rohlmann et al. [16], that also used finite element method. More FEM studies focusing on the IVD have been carried out over the years [10].

A few years later, the computational mechanics' scientific community started to focus their attention on other advanced discretization techniques, such as the meshless methods. In this work, a meshless method is used to perform the structural analysis of the IVD and obtain the corresponding variable fields – the radial point interpolation method (RPIM). The RPIM emerged as a promising technique due to its sensitivity to the element's distortion [17]. The RPIM has been successfully applied to 1D and 2D solid mechanics, plate and shell structures, problems of smart materials, geometrically non-linear problems, material non-linear problems in civil engineering [18], and biomechanics related topics, such as the simulation of human chromosomes [19] or even a 2D stress analysis of zirconia dental implants [20].

In the present work, an analysis of the pressure in the IVD will be performed through the use of both RPIM and FEM, in order to study the effect of the pressure exerted by the vertebrae when applied in certain positions and when the mechanical properties of the disc are varied.

2. Meshless Methods and Model Discretization

2.1. RPIM formulation

Due to continuous advances in numerical techniques and computational technology, FEM is able to simulate several distinct scenarios in a realistic way [8]. Despite the good results obtained using FEM, there are some mesh-related problems that can be minimized if a meshless approach is considered [21]. In opposition to FEM, in the meshless methods the nodes can be arbitrary distributed, since the field functions are approximated within an influence-domain rather than an element. Throughout the years, several interpolation meshless methods were developed, and one of the most relevant is the RPIM [22]. By meshless methods, models can be built using only nodes, without the need of a pre-established mesh. This makes meshless methods very effective in modeling large deformations, mesh-transient problems and fracture problems, especially for highly heterogeneous materials [21].

The RPIM constructs its shape functions using the radial point interpolator technique [22]. Thus, the variable field $h(\mathbf{x}_I)$ of an integration point $\mathbf{x}_I$ can be interpolated with the following expression:

$$h(\mathbf{x}_I) = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot a_i + \sum_{j=1}^m p_j(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot b_j = \mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{a} + \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{b} \quad (1)$$

In which, n represents the number of nodes inside the influence-domain of $\mathbf{x}_I$, m is the number of monomial of the polynomial basis functions $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_I)$, respectively. The radial basis functions (RBF) is represented by $\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}_I)$ and $\mathbf{a}$ and $\mathbf{b}$ are the non-constant coefficients of $\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}_I)$ and $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_I)$, respectively: $\mathbf{a} = \{a_1 \ \dots \ a_n\}^T$ and $\mathbf{b} = \{b_1 \ \dots \ b_m\}^T$. The RBF used in this work is the Multi-Quadratics RBF (MQ-RBF), which can be represented as,

$$r_i(\mathbf{x}_I) = r(d_{iI}) = (d_{iI}^2 + c^2)^p \quad (2)$$

Being, d_{iI} the Euclidean norm between node $\mathbf{x}_i$ and the integration point $\mathbf{x}_I$:

$$d_{iI} = \sqrt{(x_i - x_I)^2 + (y_i - y_I)^2 + (z_i - z_I)^2} \quad (3)$$

and c and p the MQ-RBF shape parameters, already optimized for elasto-static problems in previous works: $p = 0.9999$ and $c = 0.0001$ [22]. In this work, a constant polynomial basis functions is used. Thus, $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \{1\}$ and $m = 1$.

To construct the RPI function of integration point $\mathbf{x}_I$, it is necessary to apply Eq. (1) to each k node inside the influence-domain of $\mathbf{x}_I$.

$$h(\mathbf{x}_k) = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i(\mathbf{x}_k) \cdot a_i + \sum_{j=1}^m p_j(\mathbf{x}_k) \cdot b_j = h_k, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (4)$$

Notice that h_k is the nodal variable value. To ensure a unique solution, the following equation must be included in the interpolating system of equations [22]:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n p_j(\mathbf{x}_i) \cdot a_i = 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (5)$$

Allowing to write the following system of equations,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{P} \\ \mathbf{P}^T & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{a} \\ b \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{h} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{G} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{a} \\ b \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{h} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Being $\mathbf{G}$ the moment matrix. Matrices $\mathbf{R}$ and $\mathbf{P}$ and vector $\mathbf{h}$ are defined as,

$$\mathbf{R}_{[n \times n]} = \begin{bmatrix} R(r_{11}) & R(r_{12}) & \dots & R(r_{1n}) \\ R(r_{21}) & R(r_{22}) & \dots & R(r_{2n}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ R(r_{n1}) & R(r_{n2}) & \dots & R(r_{nn}) \end{bmatrix}; \quad \mathbf{P}_{[n \times 1]} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}; \quad \mathbf{h}_{[n \times 1]} = \begin{bmatrix} h_1 \\ h_2 \\ \vdots \\ h_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Solving Eq. (6) it is possible to obtain the non-constant coefficients:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{a} \\ b \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{G}^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{h} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

To assure that $\mathbf{G}$ is invertible, it is necessary that $m \leq n$. Since in this work, the number of nodes inside the influence domain is always much higher than the number of polynomial terms of the polynomial basis $\mathbf{p}$, ($m = 1$), this condition is always largely satisfied. Substituting $\mathbf{a}$ and b , into Eq. (1), the shape functions vector $\phi(\mathbf{x}_I)$ of the integration point $\mathbf{x}_I$ is obtained:

$$h(\mathbf{x}_I) = \{\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T; \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T\} \mathbf{G}^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{h} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} = \{\boldsymbol{\Phi}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T; \boldsymbol{\Psi}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T\} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{h} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

being $\boldsymbol{\Phi}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \{\boldsymbol{\Phi}_1(\mathbf{x}_I), \boldsymbol{\Phi}_2(\mathbf{x}_I), \dots, \boldsymbol{\Phi}_n(\mathbf{x}_I)\}$ and the residual, $\boldsymbol{\Psi}(\mathbf{x}_I)$, defined by $\boldsymbol{\Psi}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \{\psi_I(\mathbf{x}_I)\}$. The RPI shape functions possess the delta Kronecker property, which allows to exactly impose the essential and natural boundary conditions using penalty techniques, and possess compact support, leading to banded system of equations. Details on the construction of RPI shape functions and corresponding numerical properties can be found in the literature [22].

2.2. Elasto-static system of equations

After discretizing the problem domain and determining the shape functions, the equilibrium equations based on the principle of virtual displacements can be developed,

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \boldsymbol{\sigma} d\Omega - \int_{\Omega} \delta \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{b} d\Omega - \int_{\Omega} \delta \mathbf{u}^T \bar{\mathbf{t}} d\Gamma_t = 0 \quad (10)$$

where Ω represents the domain of the problem and Γ_t the traction boundary. The strain vector is defined with $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ and the stress vector with $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$. The displacement fields is represented with, $\mathbf{u}$, the body force vector as $\mathbf{b}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{t}}$ is the traction vector representing the external force applied on the natural boundary. Using the generalized Hooke's law, the relation between $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ can be established,

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_I) \Leftrightarrow \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx}(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ \varepsilon_{yy}(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ \varepsilon_{zz}(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ \gamma_{xy}(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ \gamma_{yz}(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ \gamma_{zx}(\mathbf{x}_I) \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{d}{dx} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{d}{dy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{d}{dz} \\ \frac{d}{dy} & \frac{d}{dx} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{d}{dz} & \frac{d}{dy} \\ \frac{d}{dz} & 0 & \frac{d}{dx} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ v(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ w(\mathbf{x}_I) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

and then,

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{c} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \Leftrightarrow \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx}(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ \varepsilon_{yy}(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ \varepsilon_{zz}(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ \gamma_{xy}(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ \gamma_{yz}(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ \gamma_{zx}(\mathbf{x}_I) \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E} & -\frac{\nu}{E} & -\frac{\nu}{E} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu}{E} & \frac{1}{E} & -\frac{\nu}{E} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu}{E} & -\frac{\nu}{E} & \frac{1}{E} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx}(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ \varepsilon_{yy}(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ \varepsilon_{zz}(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ \gamma_{xy}(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ \gamma_{yz}(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ \gamma_{zx}(\mathbf{x}_I) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

being E the Young's modulus, ν the Poisson's coefficient and G the shear modulus, $G = E/(2\nu + 2)$. Thus, the first term of Eq.(8) is as follows:

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \boldsymbol{\sigma} d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} (\delta \mathbf{L}\mathbf{u})^T \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{L}\mathbf{u}) d\Omega \quad (13)$$

The RPIM permits to interpolate nodal data to integration points ($\mathbf{x}_I$) using the shape functions of ($\mathbf{x}_I$), allowing to define the virtual displacement $\delta \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_I)$ with the interpolation function, $\boldsymbol{\phi}(\mathbf{x}_i)$,

$$\delta \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \delta \mathbf{u}_I = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_1(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 & 0 & \dots & \phi_n(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \phi_1(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 & \dots & 0 & \phi_n(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \phi_1(\mathbf{x}_I) & \dots & 0 & 0 & \phi_n(\mathbf{x}_I) \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta u_1 \\ \delta v_1 \\ \delta w_1 \\ \vdots \\ \delta u_n \\ \delta v_n \\ \delta w_n \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{H}_I \delta \mathbf{u} \quad (14)$$

Notice that in a 3D analysis, each node $\mathbf{x}_i$ possesses three degrees of freedom: $\mathbf{u}_i = \{u_i, v_i, w_i\}^T$. Assuming $\mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{H}_I = \mathbf{B}_I$, Eq.(11) becomes,

$$\int_{\Omega} (\delta \mathbf{L}\mathbf{u})^T \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{L}\mathbf{u}) d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} (\mathbf{L}\mathbf{H}_I \delta \mathbf{u})^T \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{L}\mathbf{H}_I \mathbf{u}) d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \delta (\mathbf{B}_I \mathbf{u})^T \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{B}_I \mathbf{u}) d\Omega = \delta \mathbf{u}^T \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}_I^T \mathbf{c} \mathbf{B}_I \mathbf{u} d\Omega \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{B}_I$ is the deformability matrix of the interest point $\mathbf{x}_I$ and can be written as,

$$\mathbf{B}_I = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{d\phi_1(x_I)}{dx} & 0 & 0 & \dots & \frac{d\phi_n(x_I)}{dx} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{d\phi_1(x_I)}{dy} & 0 & \dots & 0 & \frac{d\phi_n(x_I)}{dy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{d\phi_1(x_I)}{dz} & \dots & 0 & 0 & \frac{d\phi_n(x_I)}{dz} \\ \frac{d\phi_1(x_I)}{dy} & \frac{d\phi_1(x_I)}{dx} & 0 & \dots & \frac{d\phi_n(x_I)}{dy} & \frac{d\phi_n(x_I)}{dx} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{d\phi_1(x_I)}{dz} & \frac{d\phi_1(x_I)}{dy} & \dots & 0 & \frac{d\phi_n(x_I)}{dz} & \frac{d\phi_n(x_I)}{dy} \\ \frac{d\phi_1(x_I)}{dz} & 0 & \frac{d\phi_1(x_I)}{dx} & \dots & \frac{d\phi_n(x_I)}{dz} & 0 & \frac{d\phi_n(x_I)}{dx} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

It is possible to discretize the integral of Eq. (13) by dividing the volume domain, Ω , into several subdomains, Ω_I , which corresponds to the physical volume occupied by each integration point, $\mathbf{x}_I$. The volume of such a subdomain is represented by the integration weight, $\hat{\omega}_I$, of the corresponding integration point, $\mathbf{x}_I$. Thus, the discretized version of Eq. (13) can be written as,

$$\delta \mathbf{u}^T \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}_I^T \mathbf{c} \mathbf{B}_I \mathbf{u} \, d\Omega = \delta \mathbf{u}^T \sum_{I=1}^{N_Q} [\hat{\omega}_I \mathbf{B}_I^T \mathbf{c} \mathbf{B}_I] \mathbf{u} = \delta \mathbf{u}^T \sum_{I=1}^{N_Q} [\mathbf{K}_I] \mathbf{u} = \delta \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{K} \mathbf{u} \quad (17)$$

where N_Q represents the total number of integration points. The local stiffness matrix $\mathbf{K}_I$ is then assembled into the global stiffness matrix, $\mathbf{K}$. Regarding the second and third terms of Eq. (10), the body volume forces are neglected, so only the third term is developed,

$$\int_{\Gamma_t} \delta \mathbf{u}^T \bar{\mathbf{t}} \, d\Gamma_t = \delta \mathbf{u}^T \int_{\Gamma_t} \mathbf{H}^T \bar{\mathbf{t}} \, d\Gamma_t = \delta \mathbf{u}^T \sum_{I=1}^{N_Q^*} [\hat{\omega}_I \mathbf{H}_I^T \bar{\mathbf{t}}] = \delta \mathbf{u}^T \sum_{I=1}^{N_Q^*} [\mathbf{f}_I] = \delta \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{f} \quad (18)$$

where N_Q^* represents the number of integration points along the natural boundary. Thus, substituting Eq. (17) and (18) into Eq. (10), it is possible to establish the final discrete system of equations,

$$\delta \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{K} \mathbf{u} - \delta \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{f} = 0 \Rightarrow \mathbf{K} \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{f} \quad (19)$$

and then obtain the displacement field, $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{K}^{-1} \mathbf{f}$.

2.3. Model construction

To obtain the IVD computational model, an anonymized CT image was used to perform the manual segmentation in the 3D Slicer® software, and obtain a IVD representation, in the STL format, as shown in Fig.1(a). This STL file is then opened in Meshmixer® software where possible mesh problems, such as holes and ill-conditioned triangles, are eliminated; the surface mesh of the STL is smoothed and significantly reduced (by decreasing the vertices and number of surface triangles), obtaining the representation presented in Fig.1(b), with 819 vertices and 1634 triangles. It should be noted that, at this stage, only a triangular surface mesh was obtained, and it is necessary to discretize the problem domain using solid elements, such as tetrahedral elements, so that a 3D analysis is allowed. For this, the FEMAP® student version software is used, and an IVD representation was obtained, as shown in Fig.1(c), with 1501 nodes and 6306 elements. This file was saved in INP format, so that it can be imported into the academic meshless software FEMAS® (cmech.webs.com), where the pressure analysis will be performed, more specifically at the points marked in red in Fig.1(d).

Fig.1 - IVD model (a) after manual segmentation in Slicer® software; (b) after smoothing and correcting errors in Meshmixer® software; (c) after application of tetrahedral mesh in FEMAP® software; (d) Region of interest for the analysis.

The materials and their properties were defined in the FEMAS® software. The model consists of two types of materials, corresponding to the NP and the AF. As previously mentioned, when a IVD degenerates, its composition changes, leading to a change in the mechanical properties [10],[11]. Table 1 shows the different mechanical properties for a healthy IVD, identified as hydrated (Case A), and for a degenerated IVD (Case B), identified as dehydrated. Based on the literature, both Young's modulus (E) and Poisson's coefficient (ν) were defined [11], [23], [24]. Throughout this analysis, it was assumed that the IVD model presents isotropic, homogeneous characteristics and linear elastic behavior.

Table 1 - Mechanical properties of the IVD materials.

	Hydrated (Case A)		Dehydrated (Case B)	
	E (MPa)	ν	E (MPa)	ν
NP	1.00	0.49	1.66	0.40
AF	2.56	0.40	12.29	0.35

In order to estimate the value of E for the simulations, it was necessary to understand that the NP accounts for 40%-50% of the volume of the adult IVD [5]. Considering that NP represents 50% of the volume, it is subsequently possible to assume that AF represents the other 50%. Thus, using the volume fraction concept, it is possible to estimate the homogenized Young's moduli of both healthy and degenerated IVDs cases.

$$E = \frac{E_{NP} \cdot V_{NP} + E_{AF} \cdot V_{AF}}{V_{NP} + V_{AF}} \quad (20)$$

Being E_i the Young's modulus of material i , and V_i the corresponding volume fraction. Regarding ν , it is possible to say that the value that was used results from the average of the NP and AF values, in both healthy and degenerated IVDs.

2.4. Model construction

After establishing the mechanical properties, it is necessary to define the essential and natural boundary conditions (Fig.(2)). The first ones are the restrictions applied to the inferior part of the IVD so that it does not move freely. In this particular case, no displacement was allowed in any direction, as shown in Fig.2(a).

The natural boundary conditions concern the forces that are applied to the superior part of the IVD, for the different cases studied. The first load case, Fig.2(b), concerns a normal pressure applied along Oz axis on the top of the IVD. The second load case, Fig.2(c), corresponds to a force applied with a 45° angle with respect to the IVD plane, simulating a tilted movement to the side. The third load case, Fig.2(d), simulates a pure shear solicitation, by applying a force contained in the IVD plane. It should be mentioned that, in all cases, it was assumed a straight sitting position, actively straightening the back.

Regarding the load magnitudes, previous works address such matter, such as the work of Wilke et al. [25]. Thus, for the body position mentioned before, the pressure applied to an area of 1800 mm^2 , is approximately 0.55 MPa . Thus, knowing the area of the natural boundary of load case 1 ($A = 500 \text{ mm}^2$), it is possible to estimate the total force applied to the IVD: $F = p \cdot A = 0.55 \cdot 500 = 275 \text{ N}$. All load cases possess the same force magnitude, only the force direction is modified.

Fig.2 – (a) constrained boundary; (b) load case 1; (c) load case 2; (d) load case 3.

3. Results

After the RPIM and FEM analysis, displacements, stress and strain fields are obtained. In this section, the results obtained are presented. In Fig.3 and Fig.4 are presented the colored maps of the effective distribution of von Mises stresses, for a healthy IVD and degenerated IVD, respectively, when different loads are applied, as described before.

The von Mises equivalent stress (σ_{ef}) and equivalent strain (ϵ_{eq}), both acquired along the interest region depicted in Fig.1(d), are shown in Fig.5, respectively.

Table 2 shows the different values of σ_1 and σ_3 , representing the maximum tensile and compressive stress in the model, correspondingly. Besides that, it is also possible to observe information regarding the average value of each

principal stress (σ_1 and σ_3). Principal stresses are presented due to its importance in biotissues. For instances in the IVD, the fibers oriented respecting the principal stress directions.

Table 2 – Principal stress σ_1, σ_3 [MPa] and correspondent average values, $\bar{\sigma}_1$ and $\bar{\sigma}_3$ [MPa] for the six different study cases.

	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2	B3
σ_1	0.4303	2.7703	4.8263	1.478	4.7996	5.278
σ_3	-3.8462	-8.096	-4.8449	-5.4609	-12.7272	-3.9345
$\bar{\sigma}_1$	0.0555	0.3628	0.3615	0.1661	0.5378	-0.4068
$\bar{\sigma}_3$	-0.367	-0.346	-0.421	-0.458	-0.4068	-0.4638

Fig.3 – Colored maps of the effective distribution of von Mises stresses (MPa) for healthy IVD (A) in 3 different load cases(1, 2 and 3) for (a) FEM analysis; (b) RPIM analysis.

4. Discussion

The main goal of this work was to develop an IVD model, using several softwares, to perform an elasto-static meshless analysis. Additionally, two IVD conditions were assumed, aiming to understand the impact of the material properties on the stress and strain variable fields. In order to validate the meshless analysis, the models were also analyzed using the well-known, and extensively validated, FEM.

Taking into consideration the results presented in Fig.(3), it is possible to assume that the higher von Mises stress are obtained for a degenerated IVD when a person is tilted to the side (case B2), for FEM and RPIM analyzes, with 5.987 MPa and 3.914 MPa, respectively. By contrast, smaller values for the von Misses stress were obtained for a healthy IVD when the pressure is exerted on the entire superior part of the IVD, for both FEM and RPIM analyzes, with 1.212 MPa and 1.165 MPa, respectively. It is possible to conclude that a degenerated IVD presents higher stress values than a healthy IVD, as it was showed in the study performed by Cai et al. [9], Park et al. [26] and Rohlmann et al. [16].

Through the analysis of Fig.(4), it is possible to conclude that when the stresses in cases A and B are compared, both from the FEM and from the RPIM analysis, they are equivalent, but the same does not happen with strains.

Analyzing Fig.(5), it is possible to observe that the maximum tensile stress is obtained for a degenerated IVD when a shear force is applied (B3). Also, the minimum compressive stress is obtained for a degenerated IVD, but this time when a tilted movement to the side occurs (B2). Besides that, it is also possible to visualize that the maximum average value for σ_1 was 0.538 MPa (B2) and the minimum value for σ_3 was -0.464 MPa (B3).

Fig.4 – Colored maps of the effective distribution of von Mises stresses (MPa) for a degenerated IVD (A) in 3 different load cases(1, 2 and 3) for (a) FEM analysis; (b) RPIM analysis.

Fig.5 - Graphical representations of the von Mises's effective stress (MPa) for the length of the region of interest using (a) FEM analysis; (b) RPIM analysis.

5. Conclusion

The main objectives of the present work were: to compare the performance of a meshless method (RPIM) and the FEM; and to study the application of different pressures in both healthy and degenerated IVDs. To achieve this goal, a 3D model of an IVD was constructed and analyzed using an elasto-static formulation. When analyzing the different stress fields obtained, it was possible to corroborate the literature, in the sense that a degenerated IVD (higher Young's

modulus) presents higher von Mises stresses than a healthy IVD (smaller Young's modulus). It was also possible to conclude that when comparing the values obtained by FEM with RPIM, they do not vary significantly. Besides that, for a region of interest, stress and strain will not present similar behavior, because mechanical properties are not the same.

With this study, it was possible to observe the advantages of using discretization techniques and simulation in the medical field, as well as the robustness and maturity of meshless methods in the biomechanical simulation of biological structures. However, it is important to refer that, involving meshless methods, no similar studies were found in literature, which hinders a more detailed comparison and validations of the RPIM performance.

Fig.6 - Graphical representations of the equivalent strain (MPa) for the length of the region of interest using (a) FEM analysis; (b) RPIM analysis.

References

- [1] B. R. Whatley and X. Wen, "Intervertebral disc (IVD): Structure, degeneration, repair and regeneration," *Mater. Sci. Eng. C*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 61–77, 2012.
- [2] M. Bashkuev, S. Reitmaier, and H. Schmidt, "Relationship between intervertebral disc and facet joint degeneration: A probabilistic finite element model study," *J. Biomech.*, vol. 102, p. 109518, 2020.
- [3] C. S. C. F. França, "Modelo Matemático da Coluna Vertebral," 2010.
- [4] D. G. de Oliveira, "Análise mecânica da coluna lombar com ênfase nos esforços nos ligamentos," p. 141, 2013.
- [5] N. Newell, J. P. Little, A. Christou, M. A. Adams, C. J. Adam, and S. D. Masouros, "Biomechanics of the human intervertebral disc: A review of testing techniques and results," *J. Mech. Behav. Biomed. Mater.*, vol. 69, pp. 420–434, 2017.
- [6] B. Yang and G. D. O'Connell, "Intervertebral disc swelling maintains strain homeostasis throughout the annulus fibrosus: A finite element analysis of healthy and degenerated discs," *Acta Biomater.*, vol. 100, pp. 61–74, 2019.
- [7] C. O. S. Carneiro, "Caracterização do comportamento mecânico de uma vértebra lombar; com e sem cimentação," Faculdade de Engenharia da Universidade do Porto, 2014.
- [8] Q. H. Zhang and E. C. Teo, "Finite element application in implant research for treatment of lumbar degenerative disc disease," *Med. Eng. Phys.*, vol. 30, no. 10, pp. 1246–1256, 2008.
- [9] X. yi Cai et al., "Biomechanical Effect of L4–L5 Intervertebral Disc Degeneration on the Lower Lumbar Spine: A Finite Element Study," *Orthop. Surg.*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 917–930, 2020.
- [10] W. M. Park, K. Kim, and Y. H. Kim, "Effects of degenerated intervertebral discs on intersegmental rotations, intradiscal pressures, and facet joint forces of the whole lumbar spine," *Comput. Biol. Med.*, vol. 43, no. 9, pp. 1234–1240, 2013.
- [11] F. F. Lemos, "Influência da desidratação no comportamento mecânico do disco intervertebral lombar," 2011.
- [12] T. Guehring, F. Unglaub, H. Lorenz, G. Omlor, H. J. Wilke, and M. W. Kroeber, "Intradiscal pressure measurements in normal discs, compressed discs and compressed discs treated with axial posterior disc distraction: An experimental study on the rabbit lumbar spine model," *Eur. Spine J.*, vol. 15, no. 5, pp. 597–604, 2006.
- [13] K. Sato, S. Kikuchi, and T. Yonezawa, "In vivo intradiscal pressure measurement in healthy individuals and in patients with ongoing back problems," *Spine (Phila. Pa. 1976)*, vol. 24, no. 23, pp. 2468–2474, 1999.
- [14] H. Schmidt, A. Kettler, F. Heuer, U. Simon, L. Claes, and H. J. Wilke, "Intradiscal pressure, shear strain, and fiber strain in the intervertebral disc under combined loading," *Spine (Phila. Pa. 1976)*, vol. 32, no. 7, pp. 748–755, 2007.
- [15] A. Nachemson, "Load on lumbar disks in various positions," *Clinical Orthopaedics and Related Research*, vol. 45, pp. 107–122, 1966.
- [16] A. Rohlmann, T. Zander, H. Schmidt, H. J. Wilke, and G. Bergmann, "Analysis of the influence of disc degeneration on the mechanical behaviour of a lumbar motion segment using the finite element method," *J. Biomech.*, vol. 39, no. 13, pp. 2484–2490, 2006.

- [17] R. El Kadmiri, Y. Belaasilia, A. Timesli, and M. S. Kadiri, “A coupled Meshless-FEM method based on strong form of Radial Point Interpolation Method (RPIM),” in *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2021, vol. 1743, no. 1.
- [18] G. R. Liu, G. Y. Zhang, Y. T. Gu, and Y. Y. Wang, “A meshfree radial point interpolation method (RPIM) for three-dimensional solids,” *Comput. Mech.*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 421–430, 2005.
- [19] A. C. S. Veiga, J. Belinha, and R. . N. Jorge, *BIOMECHANICAL SIMULATION OF HUMAN CHROMOSOMES*. 2019.
- [20] L. Gonçalves Piqueiro and P. Jorge Américo Oliveira Pinto Belinha Professor Renato Manuel Natal Jorge, “A 2D Stress Analysis of Zirconia Dental Implants: A Comparison Study,” 2016.
- [21] J. D. Lee, Y. Chen, X. Zeng, A. Eskandarian, and M. Oskard, “Modeling and simulation of osteoporosis and fracture of trabecular bone by meshless method,” *Int. J. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 45, no. 2–8, pp. 329–338, Feb. 2007.
- [22] J. Belinha, *Meshless Methods in Biomechanics - Bone Tissue Remodelling Analysis*. 2014.
- [23] S. Cristina and M. Plácido, “Avaliação Biomecânica das Vértebras Cervicais C6-C7 e Disco Intervertebral,” 2015.
- [24] M. N. Bureau, J. Legoux, J. Denault, and R. U. S. A. Data, “(12) Patent Application Publication (10) Pub. No.: US 2009/0177282 A1,” vol. 1, no. 19, 2009.
- [25] H. J. Wilke, P. Neef, M. Caimi, T. Hoogland, and L. E. Claes, “New In-vivo measurements of pressures in disc in daily,” *Spine*, vol. 8, pp. 755–762, 1999.
- [26] W. M. Park, Y. H. Kim, and S. Lee, “Effect of intervertebral disc degeneration on biomechanical behaviors of a lumbar motion segment under physiological loading conditions,” *J. Mech. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 483–489, 2013.